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OFFSHORE "DEVELOPMENT-IN-EXPLORATION" APPROACH ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE SALINO DEL ISTMO BASIN (GULF OF MEXICO)

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Abstract

The development of offshore oil and gas fields is currently one of the prospective, but economically high-cost trend of the oil and gas industry. The paper discusses the issue of upfront development at the stage of geological exploration ("Development-in-Exploration"), which makes it possible to improve the economic performance of offshore projects (primarily for small and medium-sized oil and gas discoveries).

Keywords: Hydrocarbons, offshore, field development, DHI, exploration, Gulf of Mexico, integrated model, development-in-exploration.

At present, compared to 1990 (Figure 1), there is a significant increase in oil production from offshore fields (an increase of more than 2 times from 12 to 28 million barrels per day), while in onshore fields the increase in daily production was 32% and only due to production from shale formations in the USA, Canada and Argentina [1]. Meanwhile, traditional HC formations have been under a steady decrease of daily oil production after the decade of 2000s. This problem is associated with an extended level of exploration of the world's onshore oil and gas basins and, accordingly, a decrease of the potential for the discovery of new large and medium-sized hydrocarbon fields in traditional reservoirs and the gradual exploitation of already discovered ones. Scientific and technological progress since the 80-90s of the 20th century has driven the development of the continental offshore (mainly the US shelf of the Gulf of Mexico and the shelf of the North Sea) in all regions of the world, reaching its apogee in 2005-2024. Offshore fields are characterized by increased technological complexity compared to onshore fields, as well as high CAPEX, which directly depend on the time of the project implementation from the beginning of exploration to the production of the "first oil".

To solve this problem, the authors consider the experience of discovering deposits in the offshore area of the Salino del Istmo basin (Gulf of Mexico, Mexico).

In contrast to the U.S. Gulf offshore, the studying area is the least explored area of the Mexican shelf. HC deposits were found mainly in the upper part of Tertiary sediments (Figure 2). The trapping mechanism is one

of the main risk factors. The presence of HC deposits is confirmed by the evidence of DHI anomalies (attenuation of a negative seismic anomaly along a single hypsometric level), AVO analysis and seismic inversion, which makes it possible to select prospective structures only by the presence of DHI anomalies at the exploration stage. This fact is fully confirmed by the results of exploratory drilling within the basin – all 15 wells drilled within DHI targets confirmed the presence of HC deposits (the largest is Zama with geological reserves of about 400 Mtons, and all the rest - from 20 to 100 Mtons). It should be noted that targeted exploration for hydrocarbon deposits by the presence of DHI anomalies is widely used in various regions of the world for turbidite sediments, such as on the Norway and West Africa offshore [2]. Figure 3 shows an example of the identification of the DHI anomaly in the Turonian deposits at the Jubilee field (Ghana) and the UM4 formation at the Yoti prospect (Mexico). In general, HC deposits in the Salino-del-Istmo basin are confined to the raised wings of anticlinal structures bounded by faults [3] or adjacent to salt diapirs. In such traps, there are signs of an anomalous seismic attribute, which can be explained by the presence of hydrocarbons in oil reservoir (DHI). In several cases, the morphological features of amalgamated channel systems are well traced [4]. The genesis of HC deposits of Tertiary sediments is associated with the movement of fluids from Mesozoic sediments along faults and conservation in the encountered sand bodies.

Figure 1. Global daily oil production by supply segment: comparison of oil production from conventional onshore, unconventional, shallow water and deep water. (Source 1990-2009: modified from Infield System, BP Statistical Review 2014. Source 2010-2025: modified from UCube, Rystad Energy 2019).

Figure 2. Example of a seismic section with the results of the structural interpretation.

Figure 3. Identification of the DHI anomaly in the UM4 formation (left) at the Yoti prospect (Mexico) and the Turonian deposits (right) at the Jubilee field (Ghana).

Analysis of the available drilling results showed that the confirmation of the resources before and after drilling varies from 0.9 to 1.6 for prospects with DHI, averaging 1.2. Thus, we can confidently claim that a direct exploration feature of the HC presence has been found within the Salino-del-Istmo basin, which makes it possible to estimate the volume of expected HC with a high degree of probability and, accordingly, to start advanced planning for the prospect or a group of prospects development and facilities.

In modern international practice, the cost of drilling one exploratory well onshore varies from 1 to 30 MMUSD, depending on the depth and duration of the drilling. In the case of offshore drilling, the price of an exploratory or appraisal well can vary from 20 to 200 MMUSD, depending on many factors (mobilization, water depth, depth of the prospective target, downtime due to technical and weather reasons, formation evaluation program, etc.). The cost of offshore drilling rigs is dozens of times higher than onshore ones, and the daily rate for drilling platforms varies from 150 to 500 KUSD/d depending on the region and water depth. Therefore, the design of offshore exploration and appraisal wells should be planned with the possibility of further use as part of the development set of wells (for production or injection).

However, the main factor influencing the economics of a project is the development where the costs can rise to billions of dollars which in turn is critical for small and medium-sized fields. Depending on the operator's approach to the offshore development, the new field can either be started up via long tie-backs to an existing facility or by installing a new "standalone" facility such as fixed platforms (jacket platform or compliant tower) or floating platforms (TLP, SPAR, FPS or FPSO). The development wells might be set up with dry trees allowing direct access to the well at surface or wet tree production systems that can be configured in

multiple ways (satellite, cluster, or daisy chain well system). Common subsea facilities can include multiphase pipelines, subsea boosting and processing, artificial lift methods and distribution systems. To accelerate the evaluation and optimization of different development concepts from a technical and economic perspective it is required to start the development system planning (FEED) within the exploration period for further preparation of the field development plan (FDP). While the economics of large and unique fields (such as Zama in the Salino-del-Istmo basin) can withstand long design periods until the first oil, then for small and medium-sized HC fields, each year before the start of production is extremely critical for maintaining a positive project NPV.

Thus, for the prospective structures of the Salino-del-Istmo basin with medium HC reserves, it is necessary to significantly optimize the process (duration) of field preparation for production. The authors propose the concept of advanced development at the stage of geological exploration (development in geological exploration), which includes the following main stages (Figures 4 - 7):

Stages for "Development-in-Exploration".

1. Prospect selection with only DHI anomalies (Figure 4).
2. Assessment and selection of the highest priority (more than 10 Mtons of STOIP) groups of prospects (groups consist of 1-5 prospects) for further development (Figure 4).
3. Confirmation of the first prospect by the drilling results and re-evaluation of the remaining prospective groups updating (Figure 4).
4. Performing a feasibility study considering the drilling results of the first exploration well for all selected prospective groups based on a conceptual integrated model (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Selection of DHI prospective groups and confirmation of the first DHI target.

5. Preparation and drilling of all other DHI prospects (Figure 5).

6. In parallel with the process of exploration of the selected prospects, a conceptual pre-FEED is being prepared, in term of evaluating all possible options of development concept optimization by considering the use of multilateral horizontal wells, construction of a Central Processing Platform (CCP) on the location of the first drilled prospect and subsea configuration of the remaining groups of prospects with connection to the main CCP (Figure 5).

7. As the selected groups of structures are drilled, the pre-FEED is updated, and a FEED is formed for Phase 1 – production from the first drilled prospect (group of prospects). Evaluation of a scenario for possible replenishment of HC deposits [5], considering the high abnormal formation pressure of oil deposits discovered within the Salino-del-Istmo basin (Figure 5).

8. Preparation and start of pilot production:

a) The first drilled discovery can be connected to existing neighboring fields (synergy) before the completion of the production platform. For this purpose, exploration wells can be converted to injection wells (since they usually perforate OWC), and appraisal wells can be converted to production wells (since they perforate the oil/gas zone with maximum NetPay). Appraisal wells construction should be planned with the possibility of further production. The appraisal well is drilled as a vertical to perform all geological and geophysical studies and ORA testing, after which a 500-1500 m side track is drilled, than a short ORA test is performed in side track and the well is conserved before the pilot production starting. This will increase production rates at the pilot production stage and accelerate the acquisition of interference between the exploration and appraisal wells during interference well testing implementation. (Figure 5-6).

Figure 5: Exploration drilling for remaining prospective DHI groups and start of pilot production.

8. Preparation and start of pilot production:
 b) By the time a production platform is installed at the first drilled prospect, the remaining prospects will be connected according (in case of success) to a technical platform located in the first drilled discovery (Figure 6).

9. Performing interference tests for wells carrying out pilot production to remove risks and uncertainties in achieving designed production levels [6] (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Involving of another discovery to pilot production and interference well testing implementation.

10. By the time the exploration stage is completed, a FEED for Phase 2 and subsequent phases is formed for all discoveries, including a scenario for the installation of an additional production platform at another prospective group, if this improves the economical indicators of the project (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Development concept for involving of all prospective groups into development.

Advanced development approach (Development-in-Exploration) will definitely improve the economic performance of the Salina-del-Istmo Basin projects (including similar prospects with turbidite genesis deposits) and achieve a positive NPV even for prospects and

discoveries with small HC resources. Pilot production for discoveries with small and medium resources is a key factor of the project success.

Globally, the implementation of the proposed approach will make it possible to involve in the development of already discovered, but "abandoned" due to the small resources of offshore fields. Also it will allow to increase the total world daily production of offshore fields by 3-10 MBBbl and, thus, compensate the decline of onshore oil fields production from traditional reservoirs.

The success of the implementation of the "Development-in-Exploration" approach is not only focused on changing the traditional oil and gas development philosophy of the Operators but also the positive involvement of the governmental regulatory authorities. In this context, motivation and support from the government institutions will be required to accelerate implementation of these changes by establishing more flexible guidelines and permissions for Operators.

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